

THE EFFECT OF CHRONIC SINUSITIS ON THE BRONCHOPULMONARY SYSTEM

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The purpose of the study: to study the clinical and immunological features of the course of sinusitis combined with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

Research material and methods: to solve the tasks set, 44 patients with mild and moderate chronic sinusitis (HCG) aged 24 to 50 years were examined, who were divided into 2 groups: the 1st group consisted of 20 patients with chronic sinusitis (10 of mild and 10 of moderate severity) in combination COPD; group 2 - 24 patients with HCG (12 - mild and 12 - moderate severity) without established pathology of internal organs.

Results: Changes in humoral immunity were revealed in concomitant bronchial pathology in patients with moderate sinusitis. This makes it possible to develop pathogenetically justified complex therapy for patients with chronic sinusitis against the background of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. Its first stage was the appointment of an individual hygienic regime of the oral cavity, providing for double brushing of teeth after meals (morning and evening), followed by monitoring the degree of dental plaque purification using erythrosine red, a toothbrush and paste were individually selected. Local therapy included the elimination of traumatic factors in the oral cavity: dental deposits, filling defects, defective prostheses. Antibacterial, anti-inflammatory therapy was prescribed (mouthwash with 0.06% chlorhexidine abigluconate solution, romazulane applications), therapeutic dressings with heparin ointment were used. In the presence of carious cavities, dental treatment was performed.

Conclusions. 1. Parallel changes in humoral immunity were revealed in patients after covid-19 with moderate severity of sinusitis with concomitant bronchial pathology. 2. The developed pathogenetically justified complex therapy of patients with chronic sinusitis against the background of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease will increase the effectiveness of therapeutic measures, prolongation of the therapeutic effect and normalization of systemic and local immunity disorders in patients after covid-19.

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